

Five granular and 4 sprayable insecticides evaluated for yellow stem borer (YSB) control

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In 1982 and 1983, five granular and four spray insecticide formulations were tested against YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas*.

GR-11 seedlings were transplanted in 6-m² plots in a randomized block design with 6 replications. Granular insecticides were applied at 15 and 45 d after transplanting (DT); spray formulations were applied at 15, 45, and 60 DT. Deadhearts at 75 DT and whiteheads at harvest were counted; unhulled grain yield was recorded.

Of five granule and four spray formulations tested in three seasons,

cypermethrin spray was most effective (Table 1). Next was monocrotophos, followed by fenitrothion. Among granules, carbofuran was most effective; carbaryl + gamma BMC was least effective. Chlorpyrifos, phorate, and quinalphos were ineffective. None of the granule formulations were

effective during rainy season 1982.

Although cypermethrin spray resulted in the highest yield (3.43 t/ha), broadcasting carbofuran and spraying monocrotophos and fenitrothion significantly increased yield (2.94-3.01 t/ha) over the untreated control (Table 2). □

Table 2. Effect of granular and sprayable insecticide application on yield, Navsari, Gujarat, India, 1982 and 1983.

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)		
		1982 rainy season	1983 summer	1983 rainy season
Carbofuran 3G	1.00	2.5 a	3.0 ab	3.4 b
Chlorpyrifos 10G	1.00	2.5 a	2.0 c	2.8 c
Phorate 10G	1.00	1.8 a	1.7 c	2.9 c
Quinalphos 5G	1.00	2.5 a	2.0 c	2.9 c
Carbaryl + gamma BHC 2+2G	1.00	2.6 a	2.1 bc	3.2 bc
Fenitrothion 50 EC	0.50	2.4 a	3.0 ab	3.4 b
Monocrotophos 36 EC	0.36	2.5 a	3.1 ab	3.4 b
Carbaryl 50 WP	1.00	2.2 a	2.1 bc	3.1 bc
Cypermethrin 25 EC	0.15	3.0 a	3.3 a	4.0 a
Untreated control	—	2.2 a	1.8 c	2.8 c

^aIn a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 1. Control of yellow stem borer by 5 granular and 4 sprayable insecticides. Navsari, Gujarat, India, 1982 and 1983.^a

Insecticide	Dosage (kg ai/ha)	1982 rainy season		1983 summer		1983 rainy season	
		Deadhearts (no.)	Whiteheads (no.)	Deadhearts (no.)	Whiteheads (no.)	Deadhearts (no.)	Whiteheads (no.)
Carbofuran 3G	1.00	8.7 cd	394.2 a	14.5 ab	139.8 a	18.5 ab	18.5 ab
Chlorpyrifos 10G	1.00	7.8 cd	304.8 a	21.5 c	187.7 c	26.5 de	40.8 cde
Phorate 10G	1.00	10.0 d	384.3 a	22.5 c	195.2 c	23.7 bcde	42.8 cde
Quinalphos 5G	1.00	9.7 d	340.7 a	18.5 c	185.8 c	23.5 bcde	41.5 cde
Carbaryl + gamma BHC 2 + 2G	1.00	9.5 d	348.0 a	14.5 ab	174.8 bc	19.7 abcd	36.7 bcd
Fenitrothion 50 EC	0.50	3.8 a	353.2 a	14.7 ab	148.0 ab	19.5 abc	24.8 abc
Monocrotophos 36 EC	0.36	6.3 bc	408.2 a	14.5 ab	124.7 a	19.0 abc	15.2 a
Carbaryl 50 WP	1.00	4.0 ab	337.5 a	17.8 c	186.3 c	21.8 bcd	44.3 de
Cypermethrin 25 EC	0.15	1.5 a	260.7 a	10.7 a	114.2 a	15.7 a	13.0 a
Untreated control	—	7.8 cd	370.8 a	23.0 c	199.0 c	29.0 e	58.9 e

^aNo. of deadhearts or whiteheads/6 m². In a column, figures followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Daylength effect on development of 4 green leafhopper *Nephotettix* spp.

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Although diapause in the temperate species of rice green leafhopper (GLH) *N. cincticeps* (NC) has been well studied, not much is known about diapause in the tropical species *N. virescens* (NV), *N. nigropictus* (NN), and *N. malayanus* (NM). The three

tropical GLH species were subjected to the daylength and temperature conditions that induce diapause in NC.

Sixty newly hatched 1st instars of each species in individual test tubes (20 mm diameter and 170 mm long) were fed 5-d-old seedlings of the susceptible japonica variety Nipponbare. The insects were reared at 20°C under 8, 10, 12, 14, and 16 light hours (LH). The nymphs were fed fresh seedlings every 3 d and nymphal duration measured daily.

Short daylengths — 8, 10, and 12 LH — did not induce diapause in the

tropical species, although development was slightly prolonged as daylength shortened from 16 LH to 8 LH (see table). Nymphal development of both males and females of NN was significantly different in daylengths shorter than 10 LH and longer than 12 LH, except that for males under 8 LH development was about 1 d longer.

The development of NV males did not significantly differ between photoperiods, but that of females was significantly prolonged under photoperiods shorter than 12 LH. The 5-d difference between 8 LH and 16